

Supplementary Material for Paper: When Does the Time-Linkage Property Help Optimization by Evolutionary Algorithms?

Proof (Proof of Theorem 2). We assume that the initial individual x^1 has less than $n - d$ number of ones. From Lemma 2 we know the probability of $|x^1|_1 < n - d$ is at least $1 - \exp\left(-\frac{n}{24}\right)$. Similar to the first phase in proof of Theorem 1, we know the expected running time to reach a solution with at least $n - d$ number of ones is at most $en \ln n$, and we also know, from Lemma 3, with a probability at least $\frac{1}{2}$, such a search solution has $n - d$ number of ones. Once the solution x^t with $n - d$ number of ones is reached, only the offspring \tilde{x}^t with $|\tilde{x}^t|_1 = n - 1$ and 1^n can survive. Hence, we know the probability of generating a survived offspring is less than

$$\frac{d}{n^{d-1}} + \frac{1}{n^d} \left(1 - \frac{1}{n}\right)^{n-d} < \frac{d}{n^{d-1}} + \frac{1}{n^d} = \frac{dn + 1}{n^d}.$$

Hence, we know conditional on an event happens with probability at least

$$\frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \exp\left(-\frac{n}{24}\right)\right),$$

within at least

$$\frac{n^d}{nd + 1} = \Omega(n^{d-2})$$

expected number of iterations the optimum is reached.

Following similar proof techniques as in Theorem 1, Theorem 3 demonstrates the performance of the $(1 + 1)$ EA on CLIFF_{dTL} .

Proof (Proof of Theorem 3). We assume that the initial individual x^1 has less than $n - d$ number of ones. Same as the proof in Theorem 1, with the probability at least

$$1 - \exp\left(-\frac{n}{24}\right), \quad (10)$$

the initial individual x^1 has less than $n - d$ number of ones.

We divide the whole process into three phases. The first phase ends when an individual with at least $n - d$ number of ones is reached for the first time. Then the second phase starts, and it ends when one of the optima or an individual with $n - 1$ number of ones is reached for the first time. If an optimum is reached in the second phase, then the third phase does not exist. Otherwise, it starts right after the second phase, and ends when an optimum is reached for the first time.

For the first phase, it remains unchanged to the proof in Theorem 1 that the expected number of iterations to reach a solution with at least $n - d$ number of ones is at most $en \ln n$. With a probability at least

$$\frac{1}{2}, \quad (11)$$

such a search solution has $n - d$ number of ones.

If the second phase starts from x^t with $(x_1^t, |x^t|_1) = (1, n - d)$, we regard it as a success if the offspring \tilde{x}^t has its $|\tilde{x}^t|_1 \in \{n - d + 1, n - 1, n\}$, and as a failure if $(\tilde{x}_1^t, |\tilde{x}^t|_1) = (0, n - d)$. Note that only when a success or failure happens can x^t enter

into the next population. Hence, for other cases, x^t will keep its current status, that is, $(x_1^t, |x^t|_1) = (1, n-d)$. Besides, once a failure happens ($(\tilde{x}_1^t, |\tilde{x}^t|_1) = (0, n-d)$), its offspring in the next generation survives only when the previous considered success event happens or it returns to our starting status x^t with $(x_1^t, |x^t|_1) = (1, n-d)$. Therefore, let T_1 denote the number of iterations to witness a success, let T_2 denote the total number of iterations that are spent in the failure event and returning back before a success, and then we have

$$E[T_1] = \frac{1}{p_1} + E[T_2],$$

where p_1 denotes the probability of a success event from x^t with $(x_1^t, |x^t|_1) = (1, n-d)$. Obviously, we know

$$p_1 > \left(\frac{n-1}{n}\right)^{n-1} \frac{d}{n} > \frac{d}{en}.$$

Now we calculate $E[T_2]$. Let p_2 denote the probability of a failure event from x^t with $(x_1^t, |x^t|_1) = (1, n-d)$. Then we know that

$$\frac{d}{en^2} < \frac{1}{n} \frac{d}{n} \left(1 - \frac{1}{n}\right)^{n-2} < p_2 < \frac{d}{n^2}.$$

Note that once a success event happens, this second phase (we discussed in the beginning of the proof) ends. Hence, we know the expected number of failures before a success is

$$\frac{p_1 + p_2}{p_1} - 1.$$

Let p_3 denote the probability to generate an offspring \tilde{x}^t with $(\tilde{x}_1^t, |\tilde{x}^t|_1) = (1, n-d)$ or $|\tilde{x}^t|_1 \in \{n-1, n\}$ from x^t with $(x_1^t, |x^t|_1) = (0, n-d)$. Then we know

$$p_3 > \frac{1}{n} \frac{n-d}{n} \left(1 - \frac{1}{n}\right)^{n-2} > \frac{n-d}{en^2}.$$

Note that only the above kinds of offspring will survive. Hence, the expected number of iterations of returning back or witness a success is $\frac{1}{p_3}$. We pessimistically consider that \tilde{x}^t with $(\tilde{x}_1^t, |\tilde{x}^t|_1) = (1, n-d)$ is reached (otherwise, the success is already reached). Then we know

$$E[T_2] = \left(\frac{p_1 + p_2}{p_1} - 1\right) \frac{1}{p_3} = \frac{p_2}{p_1 p_3} < \frac{\frac{d}{n^2}}{\frac{d}{en} \frac{n-d}{en^2}} = \frac{e^2 n}{n-d}.$$

Hence, we have

$$E[T_1] = \frac{1}{p_1} + E[T_2] < \frac{en}{d} + \frac{e^2 n}{n-d} = en \left(\frac{1}{d} + \frac{e}{n-d}\right).$$

If the second phase starts from an x^t with $(x_1^t, |x^t|_1) = (0, n-d)$, then from the above analysis we know within $\frac{1}{p_3} = \frac{en^2}{n-d}$ expected number of iterations, it moves to the case of x^t with $(x_1^t, |x^t|_1) = (1, n-d)$ that we discussed before, or reaches a success. That is, we only need additional $\frac{en^2}{n-d}$ number of iterations compared to $E[T_1]$ to move to the third phase.

Third phase exists only when $|x^t|_1 = n - 1$ is reached. Starting from x^t with $|x^t|_1 = n - 1$, its offspring $|\tilde{x}^t|$ survives if and only if $|\tilde{x}|_1 \in \{n - 1, n - d, n\}$ or \tilde{x}^t with $(x_1^t, |\tilde{x}^t|) = (1, n - d + 1)$. Note that if $|\tilde{x}^t|_1 = n - 1$, $|x^{t+1}|_1 = n - 1$. We calculate

$$\Pr[|\tilde{x}^t|_1 = n \mid |x^t|_1 = n - 1] = \frac{1}{n} \left(1 - \frac{1}{n}\right)^{n-1} > \frac{1}{en},$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \Pr[|\tilde{x}^t|_1 = n - d \mid |x^t|_1 = n - 1] &< \frac{1}{n^{d-1}} \binom{n-1}{d-1} \\ &\leq \frac{1}{n^{d-1}} \left(\frac{e(n-1)}{d-1}\right)^{d-1} \\ &\leq \left(\frac{e}{d-1}\right)^{d-1} \leq \frac{1}{n^2}, \end{aligned}$$

where the last inequality uses $\frac{e}{d-1} < \frac{1}{e}$ and $d - 1 \geq \ln n^2$ from $d \geq \max\{2 \ln n + 1, e^2 + 1\}$. Hence, we know that the expected number of iterations to reach an optimum or $|\tilde{x}^t|_1 = n - d$ is at most en , and we also know that the probability to witness the optimum before $|\tilde{x}^t|_1 = n - d$ is at least

$$\frac{\frac{1}{n} \left(1 - \frac{1}{n}\right)^{n-1}}{\frac{1}{n} \left(1 - \frac{1}{n}\right)^{n-1} + \frac{1}{n^{d-1}} \binom{n-1}{d-1}} > 1 - \frac{\frac{1}{n^{d-1}} \binom{n-1}{d-1}}{\frac{1}{n} \left(1 - \frac{1}{n}\right)^{n-1}} > 1 - \frac{e}{n}. \quad (12)$$

In summary, with (10) (11) (12), we know that conditional on an event that happens with probability at least

$$\frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \exp\left(-\frac{n}{24}\right)\right) \left(1 - \frac{e}{n}\right)$$

the optimal value of CLIFF'_{dTL} is reached in at most expected

$$en \ln n + en \left(\frac{1}{d} + \frac{e}{n-d}\right) + \frac{en^2}{n-d} + en = en \left(\ln n + \frac{1}{d} + \frac{n+e}{n-d} + 1\right) = O(n \ln n)$$

number of iterations.

Proof (Proof of Lemma 5). From Definition 6, we know that $\text{JUMP}_{kTL}(x^{t-1}, x^t) \leq k$ happens only when $|x^t|_1 + x_1^{t-1} \in [n - k + 1..n - 1]$ with $\text{JUMP}_{kTL}(x^{t-1}, x^t) = n - |x^t|_1$ or when $x^t = 0^n$. It is not difficult to see that for $x^t = 0^n$, this lemma holds. In the following, we only consider the former case. In this case, only the offspring \tilde{x}^t with $|\tilde{x}^t|_1 + x_1^t \in [n - k + 1..n - 1] \wedge |\tilde{x}^t|_1 \leq |x^t|_1$ or the offspring \tilde{x}^t with $|\tilde{x}^t|_1 + x_1^t \in (-\infty, n - k + 1) \cup (n - 1, +\infty]$ will survive. For the former case, \tilde{x}^t has better function value but still most k when $|\tilde{x}^t|_1 < |x^t|_1$, and for the latter case, \tilde{x}^t has the function value larger than k . Hence, we know that before reaching \tilde{x}^t with function value larger than k , the probability to witness a strict increase in the function value from x^t is at least

$$\frac{n - |x^t|_1}{n} \left(1 - \frac{1}{n}\right)^{n-1} \geq \frac{n - |x^t|_1}{en}.$$

Then the expected number of iterations to witness such strict increase is at most $\frac{en}{n - |x^t|_1}$. From $\text{JUMP}_{kTL}(x^{t-1}, x^t) \leq k$, we know that $|x^t|_1 \in [n - k..n - 1]$ regardless

of the value of x_1^{t-1} . Hence, the expected number of iterations to reach \tilde{x}^t with $\text{JUMP}_{kTL} > k$ is at most

$$\sum_{i=n-1}^{n-k} \frac{en}{n-i} \leq en \ln(n-k+1) \leq en \ln n.$$

Proof (Proof of Theorem 4). For the initial x^1 , if $\text{JUMP}_{kTL}(x^0, x^1) > k$, then $|x^1|_1 \in [1..n-k-1] \cup \{n\}$ or $(x_1^0, |x^1|_1) \in \{(0, n-k), (1, n-1)\}$. If $|x^1|_1 \in [1..n-k-1]$, since $\text{JUMP}_{kTL}(x^{t-1}, x^t) = k + |x^t|_1$ for $|x^t|_1 \leq n-k-1$, we know that the process to reach to x^t with $|x^t|_1 \geq n-k-1$ for the first time is similar to the first phase discussed in Theorem 1. Hence, the expected number of iterations to reach a solution with at least $n-k-1$ number of ones is at most

$$en \ln n. \quad (13)$$

Since $\text{JUMP}_{kTL}(x^0, x^1) > k$ and the function value will not decrease, we know that there are only four cases for a solution with at least $n-k-1$ number of ones, that is, $|x^t|_1 = n-k-1$, $(x_1^{t-1}, |x^t|_1) = (0, n-k)$, $(x_1^{t-1}, |x^t|_1) = (1, n-1)$ and $x^t = 1^n$ (the optimum).

If $(x_1^{t-1}, |x^t|_1) = (1, n-1)$ is reached, then $\text{JUMP}_{kTL}(x_1^{t-1}, |x^t|_1) = n+k-1$. From Definition 6, we know that only $\tilde{x}^t = 1^n$ and $|\tilde{x}^t|_1 = n-1$ with $x_1^t = 1$ will survive. Since the probability to generate $\tilde{x}^t = 1^n$ is

$$\frac{1}{n} \left(1 - \frac{1}{n}\right)^{n-1} > \frac{1}{en},$$

we know that, the expected number of iterations to reach the optimum is at most

$$en. \quad (14)$$

Now we consider the second case $(x_1^{t-1}, |x^t|_1) = (0, n-k)$. In this case, $\text{JUMP}_{kTL}(x^{t-1}, x^t) = n$. If $x_1^t = 1$, only the offspring \tilde{x}^t with $|x^t|_1 \in \{n-1, n\}$ will survive. Let p_1 denote the probability to generate a survived offspring from $(x_1^t, |x^t|_1) = (1, n-k)$. Then we have

$$p_1 > \frac{\binom{k-1}{n-k-1}}{n^{k-1}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{n}\right)^{n-k+1} > \frac{k}{en^{k-1}}. \quad (15)$$

If $x_1^t = 0$, then only the offspring \tilde{x}^t with $|\tilde{x}^t|_1 \in \{n-k, n\}$ will survive. Let p_2 denote the probability to generate the optimum or an offspring \tilde{x}^t with $(\tilde{x}_1^t, |\tilde{x}^t|_1) = (1, n-k)$ from $(x_1^t, |x^t|_1) = (0, n-k)$. Then we have

$$p_2 > \frac{1}{n} \frac{n-k}{n} \left(1 - \frac{1}{n}\right)^{n-2} > \frac{n-k}{en^2},$$

and then in $\frac{en^2}{n-k}$ expected number of iterations, the solution x^t with $x^t = 1^n$ or $(x_1^t, |x^t|_1) = (1, n-k)$ will be reached. Since once $(x_1^t, |x^t|_1) = (1, n-k)$ is reached, it will not return back to $(x_1^t, |x^t|_1) = (0, n-k)$. Then together with (15), we know that starting from $(x_1^{t-1}, |x^t|_1) = (0, n-k)$, within expected runtime of at most

$$\frac{1}{p_1} + \frac{1}{p_2} < \frac{en^{k-1}}{k} + \frac{en^2}{n-k}, \quad (16)$$

either $(x_1^{t-1}, |x^t|_1) = (1, n-1)$ or the global optimum is reached.

Now we consider the third case $|x^t|_1 = n - k - 1$. In this case, $\text{JUMP}_{kTL}(x^{t-1}, x^t) = n - 1$. If $x_1^t = 0$, then only the offspring \tilde{x}^t with $|\tilde{x}^t|_1 = n - k$ (conditional on $x^t = 0$) or $\tilde{x}^t = 1^n$ will survive. We regard it as a success if $|\tilde{x}^t|_1 = n - k$ or $\tilde{x}^t = 1^n$ and as a failure if $(\tilde{x}_1^t, |\tilde{x}^t|_1) = (1, n - k - 1)$. Let p_3 denotes the success probability from x^t with $(x_1^t, |x^t|_1) = (0, n - k - 1)$, p_4 denote the probability to generate an offspring with $(\tilde{x}_1^t, |\tilde{x}^t|_1) = (0, n - k - 1)$ from x^t with $(x_1^t, |x^t|_1) = (1, n - k - 1)$ and p_5 denote the probability of the failure event from x^t with $(x_1^t, |x^t|_1) = (0, n - k - 1)$. Then we know

$$p_3 > \frac{k+1}{n} \left(1 - \frac{1}{n}\right)^{n-1} > \frac{k+1}{en},$$

$$p_4 > \frac{1}{n} \frac{k+1}{n} \left(1 - \frac{1}{n}\right)^{n-2} > \frac{k+1}{en^2},$$

and

$$\frac{n-k-1}{en^2} < \frac{1}{n} \frac{n-k-1}{n} \left(1 - \frac{1}{n}\right)^{n-2} < p_5 < \frac{n-k-1}{n^2}.$$

From similar proof in Theorem 1, we know that the expected number of iterations to witness a success is

$$\frac{1}{p_3} + \frac{p_5}{p_3 p_4} < \frac{en}{k+1} + \frac{n-k-1}{n^2} \frac{e^2 n^3}{(k+1)^2} < \frac{en}{k+1} + \frac{e^2 n(n-k-1)}{(k+1)^2}.$$

Also, from similar proof in Theorem 1, we know that if starting from $(x_1^t, |x^t|_1) = (1, n - k - 1)$, the expected number of iterations to witness a success is at most

$$\frac{1}{p_5} + \frac{en}{k+1} + \frac{e^2 n(n-k-1)}{(k+1)^2} < \frac{en^2}{n-k-1} + \frac{en}{k+1} + \frac{e^2 n(n-k-1)}{(k+1)^2}. \quad (17)$$

Therefore, from (13) (14) (16) (17), we know that starting from x^1 with $|x^1| \in [1, n - k - 1]$, the expected number of iterations for $(1 + 1)$ EA optimizing JUMP_{kTL} is at most

$$en \ln n + \frac{e^2 n(n-k-1)}{(k+1)^2} + \frac{en}{k+1} + \frac{en^2}{n-k-1} + en^{k-1} + \frac{en^2}{n-k} + en = O(n^{k-1}). \quad (18)$$

Note that for $(x_1^0, |x^1|_1) \in \{(0, n - k), (1, n - 1)\}$, we can reuse the above analyses for $(x_1^{t-1}, |x^t|_1) = (0, n - k)$ and $(x_1^{t-1}, |x^t|_1) = (1, n - 1)$. Hence, (18) is the upper bound of the expected runtime starting from x^1 with $\text{JUMP}_{kTL}(x^0, x^1) > k$. Now it remains to discuss the runtime starting from $\text{JUMP}_{kTL}(x^0, x^1) \leq k$. From Lemma 5, we know the upper bound for such expected runtime is $en \ln n$. Hence, we proved this theorem.